

Levels of Rural Development in Sangli District of Maharashtra: A Geographical Perspective

Mrs. Manisha Chandrakant Pusavale¹ & Dr. Amol Vilas More²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Geography,

Shrimant Babasaheb Deshmukh Mahavidyalaya, Atpadi Dist-Sangli

²Professor & Head, Department of Geography,

Shrimant Babasaheb Deshmukh Mahavidyalaya, Atpadi Dist-Sangli

Corresponding Author – Mrs. Manisha Chandrakant Pusavale

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Abstract:

The present research work is focusing on understanding the level of rural development in sangli district at tehsil level. Level of rural development is the process of social and economic growth in a society. It is a process of socio-cultural, economic and environmental transformation. This study identifies the dimensions of intra-district regional disparities of Sangli district. In this paper, an attempt has been made to conduct a detailed analysis at the tehsil level. level of rural development level of rural development is computed by employing Edward Altman's Z Score formula (1968), which has been also used by David Smith (1979) for measuring the inequalities in the levels of development. Statistical technique has been used to show the level of rural development disparities within tehsils. Twelve variables have been used to measuring the status of rural development of each tehsil of the study region. It clearly shows that only Miraj and Walawa tahsil is highly socio-economically well in position because of well ranks in literacy rate, number of village having bus, health and post offices facilities, road density, MIDC. tahsil has low level of rural development, K-Mahankal, Atpadi, Shirala and Jat tehsil is affected by unfavourable climatic condition and physiography low the percentage of net sown area to total geographical area. Percentage of village having bus, health, post office facilities are very poor in nature in this tehsil.

Keywords: Socio-Economic Status, Regional Disparities, Development, Variables.

Introduction:

Rural development involves the building of human life, which includes social, cultural, religious, political and economic conditions. In India, more than 70 percent of the population resides in rural communities. When the concept of development of the country is taken into consideration, then two main areas need to be emphasized upon, urban and rural. The development of both the areas is necessary in order to lead to effective growth and development of the country. The basic objective of rural development is to organize, develop and utilize the available resources of land, water and human

resources in such a manner that an entire population is dependent upon these resources and have an equitable opportunity to fulfil basic needs. Rural development takes into account, both the economic development and a greater transformation of the individuals. With the purpose of enhancing the livelihoods of the rural individuals, there is a need to increase the participation of the individuals in rural development programs, decentralization of planning, better enforcement of land reforms and larger access to credit. Working on these aspects will a bridge the gap between rural and urban divide and upgrade the standards of living of rural

communities The rural development involves the development of number of aspects, these include, irrigation facilities, expansion of electricity, improvements in the techniques of cultivation, enhancements in the system of education, health care and medical centres and so forth The individuals belonging to rural communities lead a simple lifestyle.

The concept of rural development is a comprehensive aspect, which takes into consideration, number of factors. This term is used to mean organizing things, which bring about changes in the existing conditions in favour of a better state. For several decades, the concept of rural development focused solely upon economic change. But at a later stage, the concept got extended to take into account, economic, political, social, cultural, technological and psychological frame of the society. In other words, when focusing upon rural development, it not just takes into consideration, the development of rural infrastructure, individuals and their overall living conditions, but it focuses upon the development of social, economic, political, cultural, technical and religious aspects as well. In promoting development of these aspects, it is vital to put into operation, modern and innovative strategies, methods and approaches that are considered essential in augmenting progress in the overall quality of life of the individuals. In addition, individuals should be trained in terms of usage of technology to bring about technical progress.

The term „rural development“ is of major concern, particularly when one is focused upon promoting effective growth and development of the country. In India, rural areas are still in a backward state and number of programs and schemes need to be formulated to bring about improvements. The term „rural development“ can be used in a divergent state. As a concept, it can promote overall development of rural areas. It has

been acknowledged on a comprehensive basis that improvements in the overall quality of life of the rural individuals can lead to augmentation of rural communities. Apart from enhancing the overall quality of lives of the individuals, the other areas that need to be taken into consideration are, agriculture, farming practices, industries, factories, craftsmanship, skills and abilities of the artisans, health care facilities, medical centres, socio-economic infrastructure, and financial and human resources.

Study Region:

The Deccan plateau and the southern districts of the state of Maharashtra include the Sangli district. The Sangli district stretches 205 km in length and 96 km in width from east to west. According to the 2011 census, Sangli district has a total population of 28, 22,143, with 14, 35,728 males and 13, 86,415 females. The district's geographical area is 8572 square kilometers. Sangli district has a population density of 329 people per square kilometer and an overall literacy rate of 82.62 percent.

Fig. 1 Location Map of Sangli District

Objective:

Main objective of the study is to analyse the Rural development of the Sangli district as the tehsil level.

Data Collection and Methodology:

The present research paper is based on the secondary data, mainly obtained from socio-economic review of Sangli district, district census handbook, record of government agricultural department of Sangli district. The level of Agricultural development is computed by employing Edward Altman's Z-Score formula (1968), which has been also used by David Smith (1979) for measuring the inequalities in the levels of development. This formula in the present study is used for measuring the Rural development status of Sangli district at tahsil level as follows –

$$\text{'Z' score (Zi)} = \frac{Xi - \bar{X}}{S. D.}$$

Where,

Z_i = Z score of i^{th} observation, X_i = Value of i^{th} observation,

\bar{X} = Mean of X variable

S.D. = Standard Deviation of X variable

Selected Indicators for computing Rural development Index:

Rural development index is calculated from eight available representative tehsil level indicators of the study region. They are as follows:

- X1 Density
- X2 Literacy rate
- X3 Sex –Ratio
- X4 Road Density
- X5 Primary Health Center
- X6 Sub-Center
- X7 No.of post office
- X8 No.Of Primary Agricultural Co-operative Societies (PACS)
- X9 No. of Project MIDC

- X10 Percentage of villages having agricultural credit societies
- X11 No.of Use electrical pump
- X12 power operated implements per 1000 hect. of cultivated area.

In the second and final stage, the composite index is worked out by aggregating the component indices and dividing it by total number of indices. It is worked out with the help of following formula

$$CSS = \frac{\sum Z_{ij}}{N}$$

Where,

CSS = Composite Standard Score.

$\sum Z_{ij}$ = Z score of i^{th} observation,

N = Total No.of variable

By using mean and standard deviation composite index is categorized as high, moderate and low level of Rural development

Result And Discussion:

According to the calculation of the composite index, it has been found that some tahsils are more developed. As per the data from 2024-25 Table-1 shows the variation in the levels of rural development in the study region Though most of the tahsils in the study region remains in the very low category of rural development. Highest rural development index value is observed in Miraj (4.31) & Walawa (4.00) tahsil. Miraj This tahsil ranks well in literacy rate, it is mainly due to the relatively good position in terms of population work participation rate, agricultural credit societies, primary health Centre project of MIDC, post office.

In the Moderate categories Rural development 2024-125 included tahsils are Tasgaon, Khanapur & Palus tahsil. Moderate rural development index value is Tasgaon (3.95), Khanapur (3.26) Palus (0.49) five tahsils namely Kadegaon, K-Mahankal, Atpadi Shirala and Jat have been included in the category of low level of rural development. Lowest rural development

index is observed in Kadegaon(-2.86), K-Mahankal(-2.51),Atpadi(-2.21), Jat (-1.99), & Shirala (-4.45) tahsil. Shirala tehsil is hilly area the unfavourable geographical condition and lesser use of modern techniques. Also, percentage of village having bus facility, health facility, post

office, primary credit societies is poor nature in Shirala tehsil K-Mahankal, Atpadi & Jat tahsil Especially less amount of banking and agricultural credit societies

Table 01: Sangli District: Level of Rural development (2024 - 25)

Tahsil	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	X9	X10	X11	X12	Total	CI
Shirala	-1.38	-2.02	4.18	-1.23	0.89	0.67	0.7	1.43	-1.11	1.68	-5.68	-57.74	-53.41	-4.45
Walwa	2.98	3.05	-3.85	-0.18	3.64	3.86	1.85	8.25	0.33	8.33	1.79	24.87	48.02	4.00
Palus	2.54	4.15	-4.54	5.79	-3.91	2.78	-2.12	2.12	-1.2	-3.29	-1.22	6.64	3.29	0.49
Kadegaon	-154	0.13	2.3	2.98	1.45	-3.35	-2.03	-1.97	-1.09	-1.77	2.17	-33.71	-34.35	-2.86
Khanapur	-1.74	0.96	4.36	-1.63	-2.54	-1.23	-0.43	-3.34	-1	-3.15	0.42	45.1	39.18	3.26
Atpadi	-2.71	-4.84	2.53	1.09	-2.54	-3.35	-4.55	0.2	NA	-0.94	-5.5	-13.34	-26.58	-2.21
Tasgaon	-0.75	1.96	-1.23	1.09	0.2	0.46	0.7	0.34	NA	0.44	2.86	44.59	47.47	3.95
Miraj	7.54	3.22	-0.77	3.09	7.07	5.98	6.43	-1.02	9.58	-1.21	3.52	12.37	51.78	4.31
K-Mahankal	-2.04	-1.21	-1.11	-0.69	-1.85	-1.86	-1.35	-1.02	-1.22	-8.8	-0.04	-9.09	-30.22	-2.51
Jat	-288	-5.42	-2.28	-5.65	0.89	2.59	2.99	0.61	3.03	0.71	2.29	-19.67	-23.9	-1.99

Source: Computed by researcher based on Socio-Economic Review of Sangli District, 2024

Fig. 2 Sangli District: Level of Rural development (2024 - 25)

Table 02: Sangli District: Level of Rural Development (2024-25)

Category	Index Value	No. of Tehsils	Name of Tehsils
High	Above 4	2	Miraj ,Walwa
Moderate	0.10to 4	3	Tasgaon, Khanapur, Palus
Low	Below 0.10	5	Kadegaon, Atpadi. Jat, K-Mahankal, Shirala

Source: Computed by researcher based on Socio-Economic Review of Sangli District, 2024

Conclusion:

The study of level of rural development in Sangli district is done for the years 2024-25. level of rural development. is classified into three categories namely Low, Moderate and High. It is hereby concluded that only Miraj & Walawa tahsil is highly rural developed because this tahsil has high proportion of flat land and fertile deep and alluvial soil. Also, Miraj tahsil has ranks well in literacy rate, number of village having bus, health and post offices facilities, power operated implements per 1000 hector. of cultivated area, Number of electric pump sets. tahsil has low level of rural development, K-Mahankal, Atpadi, Shirala and Jat tahsil is affected by unfavourable climatic condition and physiography low the percentage of net sown area to total geographical area. Percentage of village having bus, health, post office facilities are very poor in nature in this tahsil.

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